

The Influence of Leadership and Employee Competency on Employees Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the influence of leadership and employee competence on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. The sample used amounted to 30 respondents. The research method used in this study is quantitative with multiple linear regression analysis. The data processing is in the form of primary data which is the result of spreading the questionnaire. Data is processed using the SPSS program. The results showed that simultaneously leadership and competence variables have a significant effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. Partially, both leadership and competence variables are equally influential not significantly on the performance of Sempoa Company in Surabaya. The research findings indicate the need for leadership and human resource competence (employee) that can be used to help improve employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya, so it manifests the main goal of the company is to participate in educating the nation through education.

Keyword: Leadership, Competence, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

A company needs information that is strategic. Such information will be used to guide and lead the company to a competitive advantage. Competitive advantage is the key to survival in today's global and future competitive environment, the identical environment of information technology and telecommunications is growing. Today there is a very fundamental change in the concept of business universally, the company is no longer merely product-oriented but more focused on customer satisfaction oriented, where the company seeks to achieve the form of satisfaction and fulfillment of customer needs.

On the other hand, humans recognize that most of life's goals are difficult to accomplish when it comes to self-implementation. This is closely related to the emergence of individual human motivation to achieve these goals through cooperation. The establishment of this partnership is because there is hope that through joint efforts will lead to the achievement of a relatively larger goal than if the business is done independently, Gibson et al (1996: 7) states that people establish an organization for the reason that the organization is a joint effort which enables people to achieve goals that can not be achieved through individual action separately.

The development in information technology and telecommunication is very influential in the company, so the company can not gain a sustainable competitive advantage by simply adopting new technology quickly or managing its financial assets & liabilities as well as possible, but in terms of customer satisfaction, product quality and service becomes an unavoidable demand for the company. The existence of shifting the level of business competition from industrial competition to information competition is called a paradigm shift (Ary Nugroho, 1998 in Ciptani, 2000: 22). This paradigm shift will of course also change the measuring tool or reference used by the company to measure its performance.

Performance measurement is important and should be done by every company because performance measurement is the process of measuring the extent to which or how well the company does the work to achieve its objectives, so the measurement must be clear and measuring instruments used should be able to measure the success of the company in translating the goals and strategy so that the company can survive in the long run.

Performance measurement based on financial measurement alone, is no longer adequate, in essence, measurement by using financial aspects is a result, not a cause to create added value in improving the competitiveness of long-term companies.

Financial performance is only able to explain some (not entirely) of the company's past and is unable to guide the company in a better direction fully. A company is also required to measure its performance not only through financial measurement but also through non-financial measurements, such as the level of customer satisfaction, product innovation, company development, and employees. The ability of the company to meet the level of customer satisfaction, product innovation, and management of human resources will provide a strong competitive advantage for the company concerned.

Various efforts are made to the company to survive in a competitive business climate, among which companies are required to be able to realize long-term corporate strategies. These long-term strategies will be realized and translated into a series of corporate actions or activities, therefore performance measurement only from a financial perspective is no longer adequate so that a tool is needed that can measure performance from various perspectives comprehensively.

While on the other hand, the goals to be achieved and how to achieve these goals, among others, very, even sometimes conflict with each other. So that such conditions will be open opportunities for differences in views, perceptions among the fellow people who work together in an organization, in this case, a government agency. The development in information technology and telecommunication is very influential in the company, so the company can not gain a sustainable competitive advantage by simply adopting new technology quickly or managing its financial assets & liabilities as well as possible, but in terms of customer satisfaction, product quality and service becomes an unavoidable demand for the company.

Performance measurement based on financial measurement alone, is no longer adequate, in essence, measurement by using financial aspects is a result, not a cause to create added value in improving the competitiveness of long-term companies.

Financial performance is only able to explain some (not entirely) of the company's past and is unable to guide the company in a better direction fully. Management may successfully maximize operating profit, ROCE (Return on Capital Employee) or EVA (Economic Value Added) and create good financial ratios such as ROA (Return on Assets), ROI (Return on Investment), Residual Income and EPS (Earnings per Share), but often forget whether the company can survive in a long time of period. A company is also required to measure its performance not only through financial measurement but also through non-financial measurements, such as the level of customer satisfaction, product innovation, company development, and employees. The ability of the company to meet the level of customer satisfaction, product innovation, and management of human resources will provide a strong competitive advantage for the company concerned. Various efforts are made to the company to survive in a competitive business climate, among which companies are required to be able to realize long-term corporate strategies. These long-term strategies will be realized and translated into a series of corporate actions or activities, therefore performance measurement only from a financial perspective is no longer adequate so that a tool is needed that can measure performance from various perspectives comprehensively.

Elderveld (quoted Bintoro, 1987: 227) says that giving information about something that is not understood by a person or a group of people will be able to cause understanding. This understanding is expected to raise trust and confidence, in turn, expressed by the same activity. This means the leader must be able to convey good intentions to his subordinates and also the leader must be able to take and understand the two directions will grow the understanding which in turn will be able to minimize different views and perceptions of each other so that opportunities to foster cooperation within the organization can be realized. The leader is the person who works with the help of others, in this case, his subordinates. The leader does not run all the work alone but the subordinate to carry out the work. A person or a group of subordinates may do the job well as determined by the organization and there is a possibility that a person or group of subordinates is not performing the job as it should be.

These possibilities are in line with McGregor's view (cited by Robbins 1996: 2000-2001) which identifies two subordinate behavioral assumptions within an organization: first, subordinates behaving

negative characterized as X theories in which subordinates do not like work, are lazy, do not like responsibility, and must be forced to perform. Second, the subordinates who behave positively are marked as the Y theory where employees like work, creative, responsible, and can run self-direction. In this connection, the leader must be able to understand the behavior of his subordinates well, in order to influence it to work in accordance with the desired. Thus, the ability of human resources is an important issue in any organization in achieving common goals. Man in this case subordinates carries out a job because it is encouraged to meet the needs of his life. When the needs of life are met then they feel satisfied in carrying out their duties. In this connection, a leader must be able to improve the ability of his subordinate human resources to work in accordance with what he wants through hostility incentives (Handoko: 1996: 256). Incentives are the incentives that cause someone to do the work to achieve a better goal. The survival of an organization in history is greatly influenced by its leaders. That every age is better known by its leader than its organization. Like Airlangga, Ken Arok, John Kennedy, they are better known than their countries like Kediri, Singasari, United States-led. In this connection, Handoko (1996: 294-295) states that from this fact also leaders can influence the morale of job satisfaction Security. Quality of work life and especially the level of achievement of an organization. Furthermore, Gorga (1994: 125) states that the leader is a predetermined person. From the above understanding of the key success of an organization's leader, is (1) Have the ability to guide subordinates to grow the same understanding and perception (leadership) and (2) have the ability to move a person to carry out a certain activity (human resources ability).

Creative Abacus is an Arithmetic Mental Education Institute that teaches its students fast numeration techniques using the shadow abacus method. Sempoa Company in Surabaya is one of the companies engaged in the field of educational services faced by various complexities and various problems that accompany the dynamics of educational services and other service areas. For decades, service companies primarily engaged in education grew in a comfortable and uncompetitive environment. Government regulations protect the company from more efficient and innovative competitors and set prices at a level that allows sufficient return on investment and expenses incurred. The existence of changes in the business environment such as deregulation and revocation of protection by the government causes companies in related industries to be really competing in terms of efficiency, innovative, pricing, business development and so on. Customer satisfaction for Sempoa Company in Surabaya is a very important thing because the satisfaction of each student in obtaining adequate education services make them believe in the performance of Sempoa Company in Surabaya and the ability of all resources both human resources and educational equipment owned, can be utilized as much as possible to provide maximum satisfaction for customers who come. Achieving the vision, mission, goals, and strategies Sempoa Company in Surabaya has been using only reports of educational outcomes as a benchmark that can show the level of success achieved. The management of Sempoa Company in Surabaya is expected to organize the resources and capabilities to achieve competitive success through the proper management of strategic management, for the management of strategic management is required a comprehensive performance measurement that takes into account the financial and nonfinancial aspects.

These measurements can help to optimize the achievement of mutually beneficial relationships between parties company. Creative Abacus and the community it serves (students/ customers) to create sustainable competitiveness for Sempoa Company in Surabaya. The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of Leadership and Employee Competence on Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

II. THEORETICAL

2.1 Thinking and Development of Hypotheses Leadership

According to Wahyu Soemijo (1991): "Leadership is one's ability to influence the behavior of others to think and behave in the framework of formulating and achieving organizational goals in certain situations". According to James Stoner (1986), the notion of leadership is: "The process of directing and influencing activities related to the duties of the group members". Based on the opinion of these two figures

can be concluded that leadership is the ability of the individual to influence others to act and perform certain tasks. This understanding contains some basic elements, namely is:

- a. Leadership must involve others, ie followers or subordinates. Because of their willingness to receive direction from leaders, group members helps to affirm the status of the leader and enable the leadership process. Without subordinates, all the qualities of leadership will become irrelevant.
- b. Leadership includes an unequal distribution of power between leaders and group members. The leader has the authority to direct some of the activities of group members, who can not, in the same way, direct the reader's activity.
- c. Leaders can influence followers or subordinates and can direct them in accordance with the objectives to be achieved.

Leadership functions can be divided into two, namely:

- a. Task Function Task-related functions and includes functions that provide suggestions for solving and providing information and revenue.
- b. A function of Coaching The group coaching function includes everything that helps the group operate more smoothly – for the example, approving or praising other members of the group and mediating disagreements within the group.

A leader who focuses on the task function can impose his ideas and encourage the group to make quick decisions. In contrast, the group coaching function destroys the individual while responding to ideas and feelings from other group members. An individual who is capable of performing both roles will obviously become a very effective leader. The approach of leadership behavior emphasizes the style of leadership in relation to subordinates. According to James A.F. Stoner (1998) based on the way leaders direct and influence subordinates, there is a major leadership style that is:

- a. A task-oriented or production-centered leadership style, where leaders provide detailed direction and close supervision of subordinates to ensure the execution of tasks according to the leader.
- b. Employee-centered or human-centered leadership style, where leaders are more likely to motivate, invite participation, and create mutual and respectful relationships.

According to Koontz, O'Donnell, and Weirich, leadership styles can be classified according to the way leaders use their powers, there are three leadership styles:

- a. Autocratically, leaders are seen as those who give orders and who can demand decisions in the hands of leaders.
- b. Democratic or participative, the leader is seen as a person who will not perform an activity without first consulting under it. So leaders include the opinions of subordinates before proposing an activity or decision.
- c. Free Rein, the leader uses only a little power and gives a lot of freedom of his subordinates to perform activities. The leader gives power to his subordinates to determine the company's goals and ways to achieve them, the leader only serves as a facilitator.

Robert Tannenbaum and Warren H. Schmidt were among the first theorists to provide a variety of factors that they thought would influence the leadership choices of leadership styles. Although personally loves the democratic style, they recognize that leaders need to take certain practical considerations before deciding how to manage. They suggest that a leader must consider three sets of "powers" before choosing a leadership style: the power within the leadership itself, the strength within the subordinate, and the strength that exists in the situation. This approach sees the most effective leadership as a flexible leader, and able to choose the required leadership behavior at a certain time and place.

2.2. Competence

The term Competency according to Webster's Dictionary began appearing in 1596. This term is derived from the Latin word competence which means to be suitable. This subsequently substantially changed with the inclusion of various issues and discussion of the concept of competence from various literature. According to Hutapea and Thoha (2008: 28), Competence is the ability and willingness to perform a task with effective and efficient performance to achieve corporate goals. Meanwhile, according to Spencer & Spencer in Moehariono (2010: 3-4), explained that explaining that competence is the underlying characteristic of a person related to the effectiveness of individual performance in the work or the basic characteristics of individuals who have causal relationships or as a cause with the criteria used as a reference, effective or superior performance in the workplace or in certain situations.

Competence lies in the inner part of every human being and forever exists in one's personality and can predict behavior and performances extensively on all job situations (Spencer & Spencer in Moehariono, 2010: 4). Meanwhile, Mc. Clelland in Damayanti (2011: 126). According to Hendri Simamora (1999: 3), human resource management is the empowerment, development, assessment, reward, and management of individual members of the organization or group of workers. Effective human resource management requires managers to find the best way to get people to accomplish their goals and improve organizational performance.

According to Flippo (in Handoko, 1995: 5) human resource management is planning, organizing, directing, and monitoring activities, developing, providing compensation, integrating, maintaining and releasing human resources in order to achieve organizational goals. Achieving the goals of an organization depends on the ability of its human resources within the company. Man in possession of knowledge and skills in the field of his responsibility. Because this will encourage the achievement of organizational goals more quickly, effectively and efficiently. According to Handoko (1980: 5), human resource management is the withdrawal, selection, development, maintenance, and use of human resources to achieve the goals of both individuals or organizations. The goodness of an organization depends heavily on the availability and ability of Human Resources (HR) in carrying out the task or job. Human resources in this case employees who have knowledge and skills in the field of responsibility. Because this will encourage the achievement of corporate goals more quickly, effectively and efficiently, so that by itself the company will always be ready to face and adapt to any changes that exist, especially those related to the business towards the development of the organization.

2.3. Performance

Performance is the result or success rate of a person as a whole over a certain period of time in carrying out the task compared to possible possibilities, such as predetermined standards of work, targets or targets or predetermined criteria (Rivai and Basri, 2005: 14). Employee performance (work performance) is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in performing their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara, 2009: 18).

The success rate of performance includes both quantitative and qualitative aspects. Meanwhile, according to Siswanto (in Muhammad Sandy, 2015: 11), performance is the achievement achieved by a person in carrying out the task and work given to him. Rivai (in Muhammad Sandy, 2015: 12) provides an understanding that performance or work performance is the result or success rate of a person as a whole over a certain period in carrying out tasks compared with various possibilities, such as standards of work, targets or goals or predetermined criteria first and mutually agreed.

Performance measurement is a management tool to improve the quality of decision making and accountability. Performance measurements are made to ascertain whether the decision is made appropriately and objectively. The occurrence of increased or decreased productivity can be shown from this activity. Performance measurement has been put forward by experts such as Mahmudi (2005: 7), saying that performance measurement is a process of assessing the work against the achievement of objectives and targets that have been determined, including information on the efficient use of resources in producing

goods and services, the quality of goods and services, comparison of work activities with the target and the effectiveness of action in achieving the objectives.

Based on the background of the problem and the theoretical rationale, the conceptual framework of this research can be described as follows:

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework.

Based on the above conceptual framework, the hypothesis to be investigated by the author is:

1. Leadership and Employee Competence affect simultaneously to employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.
2. Leadership and Employee Competence affect partially on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Population and Sample

This study uses a quantitative approach where the approach explains the relationship between variables through hypothesis and in general data used in this study in the form of numbers calculated through statistical tests. A population is an entire subject observed in a study, which according to Arikunto (1998: 115) stated that:

"The population is the whole subject of the study, if one wants to observe all the elements present in the research area, then the research is a population study or census study".

As for the population in this study, it consists of all related elements ie all employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya. The use of the sample is done because of the large number of population and the limited time in doing the research, so it is not possible to take the population as a whole.

According to Sugiyono (1997: 57) sample is: "part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. When large populations and researchers are unlikely to study everything in the population, for example, due to time, money and energy constraints, researchers can use samples taken from populations that must really represent".

As for the determination of the sample in this study, respondents who drawn a number of 30 people aimed at employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

3.2 Measurement and definition instruments Operational

To answer the problem formulation and to test the proposed hypothesis, then the data obtained will then be processed in accordance with the needs of the analysis. For the purposes of discussion, data is processed and presented based on the principles of statistics, descriptive, while for the purposes of analysis and hypothesis testing used multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between the dependent variable and independent. In this study there are two variables ie free and variable variables are not free. As exposed in the problems and hypotheses of the above research that will formulate its operational definition. The independent variables referred to are Leadership (X1) and Employee Competency (X2). While the

variable is not free (Y) is Performance. The operational definition of these variables will be formulated by presenting the indicators.

3.2.1 Leadership

Leadership is a person's ability to influence the behavior of others to think and behave in the framework of formulation and achievement of organizational goals in certain situations Leadership is an effort to convey messages along with various information from someone to others so that arises mutual understanding in carrying out tasks in space to achieve organizational goals.

a. Leadership variable

- a.1. Leadership down is Leadership where the flow of information flows from leader to subordinate within the organizational environment as measured by: (1) Clarity of suggestion submission, (2) Clarity in giving direction, (3) Giving polite instruction, (4) Evaluate performance fairly, (5) Wisdom is easy to understand.
- a.2. Leadership upward is leadership where the flow of information flows from subordinates to company leaders : (1) Open leaders receive suggestions, (2) Giving polite instruction, (3) Readiness leaders help, (4) The readiness of leaders to make decisions.

b. Lateral Leadership

Lateral Leadership is the leadership performed by employees who have the same relative duties and responsibilities within the corporate environment : (1) Consultation Activities, (2) Suggest delivery activity, (3) An activity of submission of opinion, (4) Report submission activity.

3.2.2 Competence

Competence is the ability and willingness to perform a task with effective and efficient performance to achieve company goals. Meanwhile, according to Spencer & Spencer in Moeheriono (2010:3-4), explained that explaining that competence is the underlying characteristic of a person related to the effectiveness of individual performance in the work or the basic characteristics of individuals who have causal relationships or as a cause with the criteria used as a reference, effective or superior performance in the workplace or in certain situations. Competence, in other words, the ability of human resources is an individual attitude to empowerment, development, assessment, reward, and management of individual members of the organization or group of workers. Effective human resource management requires managers to find the best way to get people to achieve company goals and improve organizational performance.

Competence is the ability to work by integrating knowledge, skills, abilities and personal values based on experience and learning in order to execute their duties professionally, effectively and efficiently. Competence employee Sempoa Company in Surabaya is defined as the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya to manage and run Sempoa Company in Surabaya. The competency indicators are described in Hutapea and Thoha (2008: 28) as covering: Knowledge, Skill, and attitude.

3.2.3 Performance

Performance is the work that can be achieved by a person or group of people within the organization and is a determinant means in a process to achieve organizational goals. Agus Dharma in his book Supervision Management, (2003: 355) says almost all ways of measuring performance consider the following things:

- a. Quantity, ie the amount to be completed or achieved.
- b. Quality, the quality that must be produced (whether or not).
- c. Timeliness, which is in accordance with the planned time

The aspects of performance standards according to Mangkunegara (2009: 18) consists of aspects of quantitative and qualitative aspects. Quantitative aspects include:

- a. Work processes and working conditions
- b. Time spent or length of work
- c. Number of errors in carrying out the work
- d. The number and type of service delivery at work.

While qualitative aspects include:

- a. The accuracy of work and quality of work
- b. Level of ability in work
- c. Ability to analyze data or information and the ability to use machine or equipment
- d. Ability to evaluate

3.2.4 Test Reliability

The reliability test is used to find out how far the measurement result is relatively consistent. Based on reliability testing the value of Cronbach's alpha is more than 0.60. So it can be concluded that the item or question variable of this research has a high level of reliability.

3.2.5 Model Conformity Test

1 Normality Test

The normality test aims to determine whether the variable has a normal data distribution or not. To know the data is normal or not, one of them can be known by using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov approach. From the data normality test results by One Sample encoding Kolmogorov Smirnov produce significance value greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that the data in this study is a normal distribution

2 Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test is done to know that there is no relationship that is very strong or no perfect linear relationship or it can be said that between independent variables are not related. Based on the calculation obtained the result that the VIF value on the three independent variables is smaller than 10, meaning that the two independent variables in this study did not show any symptoms of multicollinearity.

3 Heteroscedasticity Test

The Heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in multiple linear regression model there is variance and residual inequality of observation to other observations. Based on the result of the heteroscedasticity test it can be seen that the dots spread above and below the Y-axis and not collect in one place only. The points also do not form a certain pattern, so it can be concluded that this study did not occur heteroscedasticity.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

After testing the classical assumption test and from the results of the data used eligible, then the analysis can be continued with multiple linear regression test. The results of multiple linear regression testing using SPSS (Statistical Program for social science) can be seen in the following table:

Coefficients(a)
a Dependent Variable: Performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	14,022	2,992		4,687	,000
Leadership	,117	,153	,162	,766	,450
Employee-Competence	,290	,170	,360	1,705	,100

Source: SPSS output

Based on this study, eating multiple linear regression equations can be expressed as follows:

$$Y = 14.022 + 0.117 X_1 + 0.290 X_2$$

4.1 t-Test (Partial Test)

The value of t arithmetic for the leadership process (X1) of 0.766 with a significance level of 0.450, where this value is greater than 0.05. Thus it can be said that leadership (X1) partially has a significant effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya (Y).

The value of t arithmetic for the process of competence Employees (X2) of 1.705 with a significance level of 0.1000 which means this value is greater than 0.05. Thus it can be said that employee competence (X2) partially has a significant positive effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya (Y).

Based on the above explanation, it is known that all variables have an influence but not significant to the dependent variable. Therefore all hypothesis accepted that there is an influence between Leadership and Competence to Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

4.2 F Test (Simultaneous Testing)

ANOVA(b)

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	42,261	2	21,131	3,907	,032(a)
	Residual	146,039	27	5,409		
	Total	188,300	29			

a Predictors: (Constant), Employee Competence, Leadership

b Dependent Variable: Performance

F-Test is a test conducted to determine the effect of independent variables (independent) together on the dependent variable (dependent). Based on the results of the calculation is known that the value of F arithmetic amounted to 3.907 with a significance level of 0.032 (<0.05). This means that jointly leadership (X1) and Employee competence (X2) have a significant effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya (Y). From the above analysis can be concluded that the hypothesis proved the truth and hypothesis accepted.

4.3 Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,474(a)	,224	,167	2,32569

a Predictors: (Constant), Employee Competence, Leadership

Based on the calculation results note that the value of R (multiple correlations) is 0.474. A coefficient of 0.474 shows the closeness of the relationship between independent variables with the dependent variable, amounted to 47.4%. While the sign of positive correlation coefficient indicates the relationship that occurs is unidirectional, meaning the better the leadership, and competence of human resources, it will further improve the performance of employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

The coefficient R2 (multiple determination) is 0.224. These coefficients show that the influence of independent variables (leadership, and competence) on the dependent variable is employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya jointly amounted to 22.4%. This shows that in this study 22.4% of employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya influenced by leadership and competence Employees. While the

remaining 78.6% influenced other variables that are not included in research such as Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Remuneration, environment, and work culture.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Mutual influence of Leadership and Employee Competence on Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya

From the results of a simultaneous test (F test) generated a significance value of 0.032 where the number is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that leadership variables and employee competencies simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

The existence of a positive influence together from Leadership and Employee Competence on Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya is closely related to the success of the President Director Sempoa Company in Surabaya formulating and implementing various policies concerning efforts to guide and encourage and drive each employee quietly and sincerely to carry out the company's activities towards the achievement of objectives that have been determined in advance by the President Director of Sempoa Company in Surabaya. This is done because the President Director of Sempoa Company in Surabaya is very aware that he achieved success is due to the help of others.

Attitude and behavior of the President Director Sempoa Company in Surabaya mentioned above is corroborated by Gorda's view, et al. (1996) which states that the leader (leader) functions the leader to perform the important task. Similarly, Robbins (1996) argues that leaders include mobilizing subordinates, directing others, choosing the most effective channels and solving conflicts.

B. Partial Effect of Leadership and Employee Competence on Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya

1. Effect of Leadership on Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

Leadership variable (X1) has a significance value of 0.450 where this value is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the leadership partially positively insignificant effect on performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. This shows that the hypothesis in this study is not accepted.

The regression coefficient of the leadership variable (X1) is 0.117 and is positive. This shows that there is a direct (positive) relationship between leadership variables and employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. Where at the time the value of leadership rose by one unit, it will cause employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya will also rise by 0.117 with the assumption that the other independent variables are constant.

2. Effect of Employee Competence on Employee Performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya

Competence variable (X2) has a significance value of 0.100 where this value is greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that employee competence partially positively insignificant effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

The regression coefficient of the employee competence variable (X2) is equal to 0,290 and positive value. This shows that there is a direct relationship (positive) between employee competency variables and employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. Where at the time the value of competence rose by one unit, it will cause employee performance Creative Abacus Company in Surabaya will also rise by 0.290 with the assumption that the other independent variables are constant.

The existence of a significant positive influence of Leadership on Employee Performance Abstract Creative Company in Surabaya above is a significant proof that the efforts of the President Director Sempoa Company in Surabaya fostering healthy Leadership with subordinates.

President Director Sempoa Company in Surabaya conveying explanations and instructions concerning advice, guidance on corporate wisdom is implemented in a polite and clear and easily understood by subordinates. Besides, the President Director of Sempoa Company in Surabaya in carrying out its leadership implemented a friendly attitude, open and willing to hear various explanations from employees about various matters relating to the process of achieving corporate goals. Coaching efforts conducted by the President Director Sempoa Company in Surabaya is also directed at the relevance of duties and responsibilities, both through consultation activities, suggestions delivery, opinion delivery, and report submission.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research and discussion that have been described previously, then the conclusion of this study are as follows:

1. Leadership and Competence Employees simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. From a result of the coefficient of R² (multiple determination) is equal to 0,224. These coefficients show that the influence of independent variables (leadership, and employee competence) on the dependent variable is employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya jointly amounted to 22.4%. This shows that in this study 22.4% of employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya, influenced by leadership and competence Employees. While the remaining 78.6% influenced by other variables that are not included in research such as Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Remuneration, environment, and work culture.
2. There is a positive but insignificant influence of Leadership on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. This means, the increased quality of leadership implementation efforts, the employee performance is also increasing Sempoa Company in Surabaya. Conversely, degenerate the quality of leadership implementation efforts, the more degenerate performance of employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya.
3. There is a positive but insignificant influence of employee competence on employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya. This means, the increased effort to improve employee competence Sempoa Company in Surabaya then increasing the performance of employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya and vice versa the lower competence of employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya decreased employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

Based on the description of the hypothesis in this study, ie there is a positive influence either partially or simultaneously from Leadership and Employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya is accepted.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

1. Share Sempoa Company in Surabaya

Judging from the contribution of employees in achieving the vision of the mission Sempoa Company in Surabaya, the results of this study is expected to be used as input for the leader Sempoa Company in Surabaya determining policies related to Leadership and in improving the Competence of Human Resources in this Employee Sempoa Company in Surabaya in order to improve employee performance Sempoa Company in Surabaya.

2. For employees of Sempoa Company in Surabaya

The results of this study can be one of the references of employees Sempoa Company in Surabaya to improve its performance, namely by increasing its competence.

3. For further research

It is suggested to the next researcher to be able to add other variables that have not been included in this research so that the result of the research can be more comprehensive.

REFERENCE

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